

IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the problem of building professional competences for the teaching english profession. The paper highlights four main groups of professional competences: cultural, linguistic, didactic and educational competences. It presents a brief summary of key skills a person should possess to be a competent foreign language teacher. Foreign language teachers should act as professional inheritors, critics and interpreters of knowledge and culture when teaching students.

Keywords: *Professional competencies, multicultural classrooms, methods, techniques, quality of education.*

INTRODUCTION

Teacher professional development means teachers' learning, how they learn to learn and how they apply their knowledge in practice to support pupil learning. Teachers can learn through participation in various courses, in school when they reflect on their own teaching and in observation of and reflection on others' teaching in co-operation with colleagues. Learning can occur in planned reflection meetings between teachers, or teachers can learn from unplanned conversations with other colleagues before or after teaching, or in parent–teacher meetings. Thus, learning may occur in various ways, both formally and informally. Teachers are asked to teach in increasingly multicultural classrooms; to place greater emphasis on integrating students with special

learning needs in their classrooms; to make more effective use of information and communication technologies for teaching; to engage more in planning within evaluative and accountability frameworks; and involve parents in schools.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The implementation of the competency-based approach is a way of maintaining a single educational, cultural, value, and vocational qualification space, as well as a factor in merging with the global educational space.

The subject of the methodology is the process and methods of education through the subject of a foreign language, the science of teaching a foreign language, the subject of the methodology for studying the activities of a teacher and a student. The main concepts of methodology are Method, method, principle. Didactics-what do we teach? the content of training is calculated. Methodology-means methods and techniques of Education. The concept of method – methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word “metodus” - “methodos”, which means paths, methods leading to a specific goal. In various literature one can find the narrow and broad meaning of the term. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense refers to the concept associated with the concrete course process of Education. It is interpreted as a controlled lesson process that covers the guidelines involved in the planning of classes and the preparation of teaching materials.

When it is called a foreign language teaching method, it is understood as a complex of activities of a teacher and a student that ensures the achievement of practical, general educational, educational and developmental goals of teaching a foreign language. The term method is used in the meanings “sum of educational methods” and “direction of Education”. While the first is used in educational theory in the sense of process methods, in the second sense we can find it in works on the history of teaching methodology. For example, the translation method of teaching a foreign language, the correct method, the conscious - comparative method, the traditional method, the intensive method, etc

Work with Video materials. Ways to work with movies and clips in English lessons. Another of the most effective ways to influence the feelings and emotions of students is movies and videos, clips, which are the most powerful psychological stimulus that penetrates into the hidden depth of consciousness. So, let's take a look at the method of working with video materials in English.

RESULTS

The results of teaching English with the Power Point presentations and with working audio materials indicated that the Curriculum Design module did not have a normal distribution. In order to establish whether there was an increase in students' level of digital competence, we analyzed the results before the experience (the Curriculum Design module) and after the experience (the Curriculum Design module), with the aim of establishing whether there were changes.

If we examine each of the areas in depth, we can see different results. Computer technologies were used by me on a par with traditional teaching aids. However, the practice of using computer programs shows that computer technologies have many advantages over traditional teaching methods. Among them are the individualization and intensification of students' independence, increasing cognitive activity and motivation, intensifying learning and creating a comfortable learning environment.

DISCUSSIONS

Digital competence has become a transversal one that every member of society needs in order to ensure active participation. It is also a key competence for future teachers. The development of digital competence in the education system means that teachers are trained in it, something that involves making them capable of using ICT appropriately as a methodological resource integrated into the teaching and learning process.

Finally, we observe improvements in most of the competencies that comprise the Problem Solving area of digital competence, related to learning to solve problems

through digital means, using technologies creatively to generate knowledge, and identifying areas for improvement in one's own competence. We draw attention to a major improvement in basic skills for teachers, such as the use of tools for evaluating, tutoring, or monitoring students and in creative teaching activities to develop students' digital competence, as well as in the use of spaces to updating digital competence.

CONCLUSION

Summing up the above, we believe that the improvement of the methodology for the formation of research competence is directly and closely connected with scientific work with students, which includes such points:

- educational work aimed at the formation in students of a complex of abilities and skills of educational and research work; disclosure of all laws, as well as methods of perception and understanding of scientific and theoretical material; the development and expansion of ideas that mastering knowledge of scientific field is impossible without active mental activity, without developing an independent approach to a thorough understanding of information;

- the organization of students' independent work on the assimilation and comprehension of lecture material, which is necessarily accompanied by self-control and introspection; the formation of a firm conviction that the strength and depth of professional training of students largely depends on the proper organization of independent work;

- teaching students to plan extracurricular educational activities with the obligatory alternation of classes in other disciplines

The conclusions made as a result of the study testify to the effectiveness of improving the communicative competence of teachers with the help of a modular training program, confirm the expediency of its introduction into the educational process in the PC system.

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